

Assessment of Ambient Air Quality in Selected Locations in Ibadan using Pollution Tolerance Indices

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Abstract: Air pollution is a critical issue affecting the entire globe. This study examined the relationship between Indices for air quality and pollution tolerance of a total of nine tree samples of three tree species collected beside three major roads at Ibadan. Nine control tree samples were collected from a farm far away (about 7km) from the roads within the same Ibadan. Particulates and gaseous pollutants were measured using Aerocet analyzer and gas monitors respectively while lead was measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Parameters of the Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI) (total chlorophyll content (TCh), ascorbic acid levels (AA), relative water percentage (RWC), and pH value) were measured using standard analytical methods. The results indicate that vehicular movements were a major contributor to increased concentrations of SO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and Pb in the surrounding atmosphere of the studied sites. The surrounding atmosphere of the studied sites was polluted by mainly SO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and Pb and the different tree species responded differently to air pollution in the sites. *T. catappa* exhibited the greatest resistance to air pollution, whereas *M. indica* showed the least tolerance. Ife-Ibadan road was of the highest pollution status followed by Sango road while Adeoyo road is least polluted. Furthermore, all the tree species along Ife-Ibadan Road had higher ascorbic acid content than in other locations, indicating a positive correlation between air quality and APTI. Additionally, the low APTI ratings of the three tree species suggest that they are vulnerable to air pollution and could be utilized as bio-indicators.

Keywords: ascorbic acid, chlorophyll, lead, nitrogen dioxide, Particulates.

Introduction

There is a perceivable increase in vehicular population and the location of industrial villages in major urban communities all over the world. This can contribute to the city's carrying capacity of atmospheric particulate matters like PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, CO, CO₂ and lead. The effects of the emissions are manifested in respiratory diseases in humans and physiological development inhibition in plant communities (Kampa and Castanas, 2008, Madu *et al.*, 2022). Plants are crucial for monitoring and sustaining natural ecosystems, as they help regulate nutrients and gases like carbon dioxide and oxygen while also absorbing environmental pollutants through their leaves (Escobedo *et al.*, 2008). Planting trees to reduce pollution and improve environmental quality is a widely adopted and effective method used globally (Hopkins *et al.*, 2021).

Pollutants have a direct impact on plant health, as plants are continuously exposed to the atmosphere, with their leaves actively exchanging gases. This makes

certain plants effective as bio-indicators of air quality and useful as aesthetic enhancements in urban areas (Mondal *et al.*, 2011). Reducing pollution is a priority for human health and environmental improvement, and one approach involves strategically planting suitable trees and shrubs in key urban areas, towns, and along highways. When selecting plants, it is important to consider visual appeal, durability, water needs, and spatial requirements, alongside their capacity to improve air quality (Hopkins *et al.*, 2021). On exposure to pollutants, plants experience biochemical and physiological changes, often before showing visible signs of damage on their leaves (Enete *et al.*, 2012). To understand how plants respond to pollution, we can examine their resilience or vulnerability using the Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI), which factors in ascorbic acid levels, chlorophyll content, leaf extract pH, and the relative water content of leaves (Liu and Ding, 2008). Since plants vary in their sensitivity to pollutants, resilient species are often used in environmental recovery, while more sensitive ones serve as

effective bio-indicators (Agbaire and Esiefarienrhe, 2009).

Ascorbic acid levels in plants can help gauge their resistance to air pollution. This antioxidant plays a role in the light-dependent processes of photosynthesis, activates defense mechanisms, and can act as a water substitute in light reactions under stress (Arora *et al.*, 2002; Singh and Verma, 2007). Ascorbic acid supports pollution tolerance by aiding in cell division, cell wall formation, and protective responses. It is also a powerful reducing agent that assists in carbon fixation during photosynthesis, with its reducing strength linked to concentration levels (Joshi and Swami, 2007). A higher pH can enhance the conversion of hexose sugars into ascorbic acid, whereas a low pH in leaf extracts is closely associated with increased sensitivity to air pollution (Liu and Ding, 2008).

Total chlorophyll (TCh) is another key factor in the Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI). A reduction in chlorophyll decreases plant productivity, leading to

lower vigor. Photosynthetic efficiency is notably affected by leaf pH, especially when pH levels are low (Singh and Verma, 2007). High water content in plants also helps maintain physiological balance during stress, such as when air pollution elevates transpiration rates (Nwadinigwe, 2014). Currently, comprehensive APTI screening of plants, both globally and in Nigeria, remains incomplete. More research across various species is needed to identify plants suitable as bio-indicators or pollution-tolerant species, which could help combat the global reach of air pollution. As a developing nation, Nigeria faces rising pollution challenges amid technological growth that has improved living standards. Taking steps to reduce air pollution has become essential. This study aims to explore the relationship between air quality and APTI values of certain tree species in select areas of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

The research was conducted in Ibadan, Oyo State, between February and May 2022. Ibadan is located in the southwestern part of Nigeria, about 130 km northeast of Lagos and 532 km southwest of Abuja, Nigeria's capital. The city's coordinates are 7°23'47"N and 3°55'0"E. The climate is predominantly wet (between April and October) while the dry episode is experienced between late November and March. Sango is the hub of commercial activities as well as a route to major markets and tertiary institutions with over one thousand (1000) vehicular traffic per day; Ife-Ibadan expressway is one of the busiest roads in Nigeria, a major highway that connects the south-west of Nigeria to the northern and eastern parts, and Adeoyo is an area which commands less than five hundred (500) vehicular movement per working day.

Air Sampling and Analyses of Air Pollutants

Levels of particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), NO₂, SO₂, CO, and Pb in the ambient air were measured following the procedure outlined by Madu *et al.* (2022). A Model 531 Aerocet analyzer was used to measure particulate matter, while A Series 500ENV gas monitor by Aeroqual was employed to assess levels of SO₂, NO₂, and CO. This was done by raising the equipment to a height of 2m above the ground at the various study areas and taking the readings displayed on the screen after 3 minutes. A filter paper raised to a height of 2m and exposed at the study areas for eight hours was used for Lead (Pb) sampling while Pb analysis was carried out using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) UNICAM model 939 after the digestion process. Air sampling was also carried out at a farm far away (about 7km) from the roads within the same Ibadan to serve as control.

Plants Sampling Procedure

Mangifera indica, *Terminalia catappa* and *Azadirachta indica* were randomly

selected from Sango, Ife-Ibadan and Adeoyo roadsides within Ibadan.

The tree species chosen for this study are commonly found in these areas and are located within 30 meters of the roadside. Leaves from three mature trees of each species were collected in triplicate at each site between 7 and 9 a.m. and were promptly transported to the laboratory in a heat-resistant container for analysis. Control samples were gathered from trees on a farm approximately 7 kilometers away from the roads but within the Ibadan

area. Leaves from three mature trees of each species were collected in triplicate at the control site

Measurements of Biochemical Parameters and APTI

Relative leaf water content, total chlorophyll content, pH, and ascorbic acid content were measured following the methods outlined by Agbaire and Esiefarenrhe (2009), while the air pollution tolerance index (APTI) was calculated using the approach detailed by Rai *et al.* (2013).

Table 1 Range of Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI)

APTI	Value	Response
A	<11	Sensitive
B	12-16	Intermediate
C	>1	Tolerant

Source: Padmavathi *et al.*, 2013

Data Analysis

ata were evaluated using a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and the means were compared using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) method at a 5% significance level.

Results and Discussion

The results in table 2 show that the concentrations of air pollutants varied between the roads studied. The concentrations of all the measured pollutants were highest at Ife-Ibadan road and lowest at the Adeoyo road. This suggests that Ife-Ibadan road was of the highest pollution status followed by Sango road while Adeoyo road is least polluted. At all the roads, the concentrations of SO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and Pb were above the WHO standard values.

Table 2 Concentrations of Air Pollutants at the Studied Roads at Ibadan

Locations	NO ₂ (µg/m ³)	SO ₂ (µg/m ³)	CO (µg/m ³)	PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	Pb (ppm)
Ife-Ibadan	0.039±0.01 ^c	0.050±0.01 ^c	9.064±2.10 ^c	30.940±5.52 ^c	39.500±6.03 ^c	0.060±0.02 ^c
Road						
Sango Road	0.031±0.02 ^b	0.045±0.01 ^b	7.059±1.55 ^b	28.120±10.20 ^b	33.400±9.30 ^b	0.059±0.03 ^a
Adeoyo	0.030±0.00 ^b	0.041±0.02 ^c	5.053±1.01 ^c	26.030±8.99 ^c	32.340±7.64 ^b	0.030±0.00 ^b
Road	0.02±0.00 ^a	ND	4.30±2.02 ^a	2.82±1.00 ^a	8.33±3.11 ^a	ND
Control						
WHO standard	0.04-0.06	0.01	10.000	10.000	20.000	0.050

The values in the table represent the means ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements. Figures within the same column that share the same letters are not significantly different (p<0.05). ND = Not detected.

The influence of air pollution on the pH of the leaf extracts of the tree species is shown in table 3. *M. indica* and *T. catappa* had significant ($p < 0.05$) higher mean values in pH compared to *A. indica* due to air pollution. Ife-Ibadan Road had the highest mean value and Adeoyo with the lowest among all tree species studied. Differences in pH values among tree species can be attributed to their biochemical interactions with the soil and the influence of air pollution. Leaf litter composition, such as lignin, tannin, and cellulose content, varies among species and affects decomposition rates, producing organic acids that can lower soil pH, particularly in species like pines (Prescott, 2002). Root exudates, such as citric and malic acids, also alter pH, with species-specific variations in the release of hydrogen ions (H^+) or bicarbonates (HCO_3^-) during nutrient uptake (Dakora and Phillips, 2002). Air pollution, particularly acid rain caused by sulfur dioxide (SO_2) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), exacerbates soil acidification and interacts

with tree-specific factors. Conifers, for instance, are more susceptible to acid rain effects due to their typically acidic litter and ectomycorrhizal fungi associations, which further contribute to pH reduction through organic acid production (Read and Perez-Moreno, 2003). Conversely, trees that form arbuscular mycorrhizal associations or favor nitrate uptake may neutralize some acidification effects (Marschner, 2012). Additionally, the production of secondary metabolites like tannins, which vary among species, influences soil acidity and can interact with pollutants deposited from the atmosphere (Kraus, Dahlgren, and Zasoski, 2003). These biochemical mechanisms, combined with the external impact of air pollution, underscore the complex interplay between tree species and their environment in determining soil pH levels. According to Ogundele *et al.* (2015), a pH range of 5 to 7 for leaf extract is known to improve air pollution tolerance, and the pH of the leaf extract in this study falls within the range (between 6 and 6.9).

Table 3 pH values of tree leaves samples collected at different Locations at Ibadan

	Ife-Ibadan Rd.	Adeoyo Rd.	Sango Rd.	Control
<i>M.indica</i>	6.90±1.22 ^d	6.40±1.40 ^c	6.70±1.00 ^b	6.30±1.90 ^a
<i>T. catappa</i>	6.70±2.19 ^c	6.20±1.90 ^a	6.50±2.00 ^b	6.20±1.11 ^a
<i>A. indica</i>	6.00±2.00 ^a	6.10±1.20 ^c	6.30±2.11 ^b	6.00±2.80 ^a

The values in the table represent the means ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements. Figures within the same column that share the same letters are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The total chlorophyll content of all the tree species varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the locations under study (table 4). The higher content of T.Chl was found in the tree species at the Ife-Ibadan Road and Sango locations, while *M. indica* had the lowest T. Chl in all the study areas. The differences in chlorophyll (T.Chl) content among tree species in the study areas may be linked to their biochemical responses and adaptations to environmental conditions, including pollution levels. High chlorophyll content in certain tree species, such as those at Ife-Ibadan Road and Sango locations, could indicate their tolerance to air pollutants. Chlorophyll biosynthesis and degradation are directly influenced by environmental stressors, including pollutants such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). Species with high T.Chl might possess

biochemical mechanisms that protect chlorophyll from degradation, such as increased production of antioxidant enzymes (e.g., superoxide dismutase, catalase) and stress-responsive proteins that mitigate oxidative damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated under pollution stress (Rai, 2016).

On the other hand, *M. indica*, which exhibited the lowest T.Chl across all locations, might be more susceptible to pollution-induced oxidative stress, leading to higher chlorophyll degradation through increased chlorophyllase activity and reduced chlorophyll biosynthesis. This species may have weaker antioxidant defenses, making it less effective at neutralizing ROS (Sharma *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, differences in stomatal structure and functioning across species

may also play a role. Trees that maintain efficient stomatal regulation under polluted conditions may limit pollutant uptake, thereby protecting their chlorophyll content (Larcher, 2003). Additionally, the nutrient status of the soil, species-specific ability to assimilate nitrogen, and overall photosynthetic

capacity can further contribute to variations in chlorophyll levels among species (Taiz and Zeiger, 2015). A high chlorophyll content may indicate tolerance to pollution as higher chlorophyll content can help plants withstand pollutants (Enitan *et al.*, 2022)

Table 4 Concentrations (mg/g) of Total Chlorophyll of tree leaves samples collected at different Locations at Ibadan

	Ife-Ibadan Rd.	Adeoyo Rd.	Sango Rd.	Control
<i>M. indica</i>	0.19±0.04 ^b	0.18±0.00 ^c	0.19±0.09 ^b	0.14±0.00 ^a
<i>T. catappa</i>	0.35±0.10 ^d	0.30±0.10 ^c	0.32±0.10 ^b	0.29±0.09 ^a
<i>A. indica</i>	0.34±0.12 ^b	0.32±0.14 ^c	0.34±0.00 ^b	0.28±0.10 ^a

The values in the table represent the means ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements. Figures within the same column that share the same letters are not significantly different (p<0.05).

The ascorbic acid (AA) content of all tree species showed significant differences (P<0.05), with variations in the levels across different exposed areas (Table 5). Tree species along the Ife-Ibadan Road exhibited higher AA content compared to those from other locations, with Adeoyo showing the lowest mean value (p<0.05). The significant differences in ascorbic acid (AA) content among tree species and

across locations can be attributed to variations in their biochemical responses to environmental stressors, particularly air pollution. Ascorbic acid is a key antioxidant that plays a critical role in mitigating oxidative stress caused by pollutants like ozone (O₃), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). Trees along the Ife-Ibadan Road, which had higher AA content, are likely exposed to

higher pollution levels and thus upregulate their AA production to neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by pollutants (Sharma *et al.*, 2012). Ascorbic acid participates in scavenging ROS and regenerating other antioxidants, such as glutathione, thereby protecting cellular structures and photosynthetic machinery under stress conditions (Noctor and Foyer, 1998).

In contrast, trees in locations like Adeoyo, which showed the lowest mean AA content, may experience lower oxidative stress or may be less efficient at producing or accumulating ascorbic acid in response to pollutants. Additionally, species-specific differences in metabolic pathways, including those regulating AA biosynthesis via the D-mannose/L-galactose pathway, could contribute to variations in AA content (Smirnoff, 2018). Factors such as nutrient availability, water stress, and inherent genetic capacity for stress tolerance might further influence the observed differences. For instance, trees with better access to micronutrients like iron and manganese, which are

cofactors in enzymatic antioxidant processes, may exhibit higher AA levels under similar stress conditions (Foyer and Noctor, 2011).

These biochemical adaptations highlight the role of ascorbic acid as a defense mechanism against environmental stress, with higher concentrations reflecting a tree's capacity to withstand pollution-related oxidative damage.

These results align with previous studies that found air pollution increases AA content in tree species (Bermadinger *et al.*, 1990; Kousar *et al.*, 2014). Ascorbic acid is a natural detoxifier that protects plant tissues from the harmful effects of air pollution (Singh *et al.*, 1991). Higher levels of AA in plants enhance their defense mechanisms and pollution tolerance (Cheng *et al.*, 2007), indicating higher pollution exposure. The increased AA content in tree species at this location is similar to the 0.35 mg/g and 2.39 mg/g found in *Eugenia jambolana* and *Psidium guajava*, respectively, in industrial areas of India (Kousar *et al.*, 2014).

Table 5 Concentrations (mg/g) of Ascorbic Acid of tree leaves samples collected at different Locations at Ibadan

	Ife-Ibadan Rd.	Adeoyo Rd.	Sango Rd.	Control
<i>M. indica</i>	0.249±0.10 ^d	0.239±0.05 ^c	0.271±0.04 ^b	0.142±0.01 ^a
<i>T. catappa</i>	0.298±0.100 ^d	0.268±0.08 ^c	0.282±0.01 ^b	0.214±0.03 ^a
<i>A. indica</i>	0.270±0.09 ^c	0.252±0.10 ^b	0.259±0.06 ^b	0.221±0.11 ^a

The values in the table represent the means ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements. Figures within the same column that share the same letters are not significantly different (p<0.05).

Table 6 shows the relative water content (RWC) of leaves from the three tree species in the three different locations. The RWC differed significantly (p<0.05) across locations for all the three species. *A. indica* had the lowest mean RWC in all the three locations, while *T. catappa* had the highest. The significant differences in relative water content (RWC) among the tree species and across locations reflect variations in their water retention capacity and tolerance to environmental stressors such as pollution, temperature, and humidity. *T. catappa*, which showed the highest RWC, likely has a robust water management system that includes a well-developed cuticle, efficient stomatal regulation, and the ability to accumulate osmolytes such as proline and sugars.

These osmolytes help maintain cell turgor and prevent water loss during stress conditions, enabling higher water retention (Reddy *et al.*, 2004). Additionally, species with higher RWC typically exhibit superior photosynthetic efficiency and resilience to oxidative stress caused by air pollutants like ozone (O₃) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) (Chaves *et al.*, 2009).

On the other hand, *A. indica*, with the lowest RWC across locations, may have less efficient stomatal control, resulting in higher transpirational water loss under stress conditions. It might also exhibit lower levels of osmolyte accumulation or weaker membrane integrity under oxidative stress, reducing its ability to

retain water (Farooq *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, species-specific differences in root architecture and hydraulic conductivity could influence water uptake from the soil, with *T. catappa* potentially having deeper or more efficient root systems compared to *A. indica* (Larcher, 2003).

The differences in RWC may also be tied to environmental factors such as air pollution. Pollutants can damage stomatal functioning and disrupt water balance by inducing oxidative damage to membranes and proteins involved in water transport. Species like *T. catappa* may possess

stronger antioxidant defenses that protect against such damage, allowing for higher RWC even under polluted conditions (Rai, 2016). These biochemical mechanisms demonstrate how different species adapt to environmental challenges, influencing their water retention capacity.

Plants with high water content are able to maintain physiological balance in the face of stressors such as pollution. The Relative Water Content (RWC) is often linked to the permeability of plant cell protoplasm, influencing the loss of water and dissolved nutrients in plants, which can ultimately lead to leaf senescence (Tsega and Devi-Prasad, 2014).

Table 6 Values (%) of relative water content of tree leaves samples collected at different Locations in Ibadan

	Ife-Ibadan Rd.	Adeoyo Rd.	Sango Rd.	Control
<i>M. indica</i>	0.762±0.20 ^b	0.763±0.15 ^c	0.753±0.11 ^b	0.642±0.10 ^a
<i>T. catappa</i>	0.789±0.25 ^c	0.790±0.30 ^c	0.782±0.28 ^b	0.618±0.00 ^a
<i>A. indica</i>	0.740±0.20 ^c	0.743±0.21 ^b	0.747±0.30 ^b	0.720±0.27 ^a

The values in the table represent the means ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements. Figures within the same column that share the same letters are not significantly different (p<0.05).

Figure 1 APTI of the tree species at the selected locations (APTIs = Sango; APTIa = Adeoyo and APTIi = Ife-Ibadan Road)

The APTI values for the three species were highest along Ife-Ibadan Road. *T. catappa* had the highest tolerance to air pollution with an APTI value of 11.53, while *M. indica* had the lowest with an APTI value of 7.13 (Fig. 1). The observed variations in Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI) values among the tree species, with *T. catappa* showing the highest tolerance and *M. indica* the lowest, can be attributed to species-specific biochemical mechanisms that influence their ability to cope with oxidative stress caused by air pollution. *T. catappa* likely has higher chlorophyll content, efficient stomatal regulation, and greater ascorbic

acid (AA) accumulation, which enhance its antioxidant capacity to neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by pollutants such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). These factors help maintain cellular integrity and photosynthetic function under stress, contributing to its higher APTI value (Foyer and Noctor, 2011; Rai, 2016). Additionally, its improved leaf relative water content (RWC) and favorable leaf pH likely aid in maintaining metabolic stability, even under pollution exposure (Chaves *et al.*, 2009). In contrast, *M. indica*, with lower chlorophyll and AA content, reduced antioxidant activity, and

possibly less efficient stomatal control, is more vulnerable to oxidative damage, leading to its lower APTI (Sharma *et al.*, 2012). These differences reflect the tree species' ability to withstand environmental pollutants through biochemical adaptations, which directly influence their APTI values.

These low APTI values (<15.0) indicate a moderate level of air pollutants in the area. Previous research has shown that trees in severely polluted environments have an APTI value of 81.10 (Dwivedi and Tripathi, 2007). The sensitivity of the three tree species to air pollution makes them suitable bio-indicators, while species with high APTI values are tolerant of pollution and can be used as sinks to absorb pollutants (Tsega and Devi-Prasad, 2014).

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study highlights significant variations in the biochemical responses of different tree species to environmental stressors, particularly air pollution, as evidenced by their differences in chlorophyll content,

ascorbic acid levels, relative water content, and Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI) values. *T. catappa* demonstrated the highest tolerance to pollution, likely due to its efficient antioxidant mechanisms, higher chlorophyll content, and improved water retention capacity. In contrast, *M. indica* showed lower APTI values, indicating its greater susceptibility to oxidative stress and pollution-related damage, possibly due to reduced antioxidant activity and lower chlorophyll content. These findings underscore the importance of understanding species-specific adaptations to pollution, which can inform the selection of tree species for urban greening and pollution mitigation strategies. The biochemical markers analyzed, such as chlorophyll content, ascorbic acid, and relative water content, provide valuable insights into the plants' capacity to cope with oxidative stress, and their use could aid in the development of more effective strategies for improving urban air quality and enhancing the resilience of vegetation in polluted environments. Future studies should focus on expanding these analyses to include a

broader range of tree species and pollutants, as well as exploring the molecular mechanisms underlying the observed variations in pollutant tolerance.

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Author contribution

Ogidan OA: Conceptualization, data collection and analysis, writing and review. Madu, FU: data collection, data analyses, writing and review. Olabintan A.H.: investigation and manuscript editing. Adejumo AA: data collection, writing and review.

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References

Agbaire, P.O., Esiefarienrhe, E. (2009) Air pollution Tolerance Indices

(APTI) of some plants around Otorogun gas plants in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences Environmental Management* 13:11-14.

Arora, A., Sairam, R.K., Srivaastava, G.C. (2002) Oxidative stress and antioxidative system in plants. *Current Science*, 82:1227.

Bermadinger, E., Guttenger, H., Grill, D. (1990) Physiology of young Norway Spruce, Environmental pollution, 68(3-4): 319-330

Chaves, M. M., Flexas, J., & Pinheiro, C. (2009). Photosynthesis under drought and salt stress: Regulation mechanisms from whole plant to cell. *Annals of Botany*, 103(4), 551–560. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcn125>

Cheng, F.Y., Burkey, K.O., Robinson, J.M., Booker, F.L. (2007) Leaf extracellular ascorbate in relation to ozone tolerance of two soya

- bean cultivars. *Environmental pollution*, 150: 355-362
- Dakora, F. D. and Phillips, D. A. (2002). Root exudates as mediators of mineral acquisition in low-nutrient environments. *Plant and Soil*, 245(1), 35–47. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020809400075>
- Dwivedi, A.K, Tripathi, B.D. (2007) Pollution tolerance and distribution pattern of plants in surrounding area of coal-fired industries, *J. Environ. Biol.* 29(2): 257-263
- Enete, I.C., Ogbonna, C.E., Officha, M.C. (2012) Using trees as urban heat island reduction tool in Enugu city Nigeria based on their air pollution tolerance index. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management* 5, 4 (Suppl.1).
- Enitan, I.T., Durowoju, O.S., Edokpayi, J.N., Odiyo, J.O. (2022) A review of air pollution mitigation approach using Air Pollution Tolerance Index (APTI) and Anticipated Performance Index (API). *Atmosphere* 13, 374. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13030374>.
- Escobedo, F.J., Wagner, J.E., Nowak, D.J. (2008) Analyzing the cost-effectiveness of Santiago, Chile's policy of using the urban forest to improve air quality. *J Environ Manag* 86:148–157.
- Farooq, M., Wahid, A., Kobayashi, N., Fujita, D., & Basra, S. M. A. (2009). Plant drought stress: Effects, mechanisms, and management. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 29(1), 185–212. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2008021>
- Foyer, C. H., & Noctor, G. (2011). Ascorbate and glutathione: The heart of the redox hub. *Plant Physiology*, 155(1), 2–18. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.110.167569>

- Hopkins, L.P., January-Beyers, D.J., Caton, E.K., Campos, L.K. (2021) A simple tree planting framework to improve climate, air pollution, health, and urban heat in vulnerable locations using non-traditional partners, *Plants people planet*, 4(3):243-257
- Joshi, P.C., Swami, A. (2007) Physiological responses of some tree species under roadside automobile pollution stress around City of Haridwar, India. *Environmentalist* 27, 365–374. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-007-9049-0>.
- Kampa, M., Castanas, E. (2008) Human health effects of air pollution. *Environ. Pollut.* 151, 362–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2007.06.012>.
- Kousar, H., Humar, N., Pavithra, K.D., Patel, A.M. (2014) Analysis of biochemical parameters as tolerance index of some chosen plant species of Bhadravathi town, *int. J. Environ. Sci* 3(1): 11-16
- Kraus, T. E. C., Dahlgren, R. A., & Zasoski, R. J. (2003). Tannins in nutrient dynamics of forest ecosystems—a review. *Plant and Soil*, 256(1), 41–66. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026206511084>
- Larcher, W. (2003). *Physiological Plant Ecology: Ecophysiology and Stress Physiology of Functional Groups* (4th ed.). Springer.
- Liu, Y.J., Ding, H. (2008) Variation in Air Pollution Tolerance Index of Plants near a Steel Factory: Implication for Landscape Plant Species Selection for Industrial Areas. *WSEAS Transactions on Environment and Development* 4, 24-32.
- Madu, F.U., Agoro, E.S., Madu, M.C. (2022) Exhaled breath condensate markers of oxidative stress in male storekeepers of chemical stores in

- Ariaria international market Aba Abia State Nigeria, *Toxicology and Industrial Health* 38 (12):801-809
- Marschner, P. (2012). *Marschner's Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants* (3rd ed.). Academic Press.
- Mondal, D., Gupta, S., Datta, J.K. (2011) Anticipated Performance Index of Some Tree Species Considered for Green Belt Development in an Urban Area. *International Research Journal of Plant Science* 2 (4): 99-106
- Noctor, G., & Foyer, C. H. (1998). Ascorbate and glutathione: Keeping active oxygen under control. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 49, 249–279. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.49.1.249>
- Nwadinigwe, A.O. (2014) Air pollution tolerance indices of some plants around Ama industrial complex in Enugu State Nigeria, *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 13(11): 1231-1236
- Ogundele, D.T., Adio, A.A. and Oludele, O.E. (2015) Heavy Metal Concentrations in Plants and Soil along Heavy Traffic Roads in North Central Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental and Analytical Toxicology*, 5, 334.
- Padmavathi, V., Sreemannarayana, S., Satyanarayana, V., Lal, A. (2013) Correlation and Path coefficient analysis in Kabuli Chickpea (*Cicer Arietinum L.*). *International Journal of applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology* 4(3): 107-110
- Prescott, C. E. (2002). The influence of forest floor properties on nutrient availability. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 159(1–2), 89–98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(01\)00794-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(01)00794-8)
- Rai, P. K. (2016). Impacts of particulate matter pollution on plants: Implications for environmental

- biomonitoring. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 129, 120–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2016.03.012>
- Rai, P.K., Panda, L.L.S., Chutia, B.M., Singh, M.M. (2013) Comparative assessment of air pollution tolerance index (APTI) in the industrial (Rourkela) and non industrial area (Aizawl) of India: An eco-management approach, *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 7(10): 944-948
- Read, D. J., & Perez-Moreno, J. (2003). Mycorrhizas and nutrient cycling in ecosystems—a journey towards relevance? *New Phytologist*, 157(3), 475–492. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1469-8137.2003.00720.x>
- Reddy, A. R., Chaitanya, K. V., & Vivekanandan, M. (2004). Drought-induced responses of photosynthesis and antioxidant metabolism in higher plants. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 161(11), 1189–1202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jplp.2004.01.013>
- Sharma, P., Jha, A. B., Dubey, R. S., and Pessarakli, M. (2012). Reactive oxygen species, oxidative damage, and antioxidative defense mechanism in plants under stressful conditions. *Journal of Botany*, 2012, Article ID 217037. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/217037>
- Singh, S.K., Rao, D.N., Agrawal, M., Pandey, J., Narayan, D. (1991) Air Pollution Tolerance Indices of Plants. *Journal of Environmental Management* 32: 45-55.
- Singh, S.N., Verma, A. (2007) Phytoremediation of Air Pollutant: A Review. In: *Environmental Bioremediation Technology*, Singh, S.N. and R.D. Tripathi (Eds.). Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, pp: 293-314.

- Smirnoff, N. (2018). Ascorbic acid metabolism and functions: A comparison of plants and mammals. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 122, 116–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2018.03.033>
- Taiz, L., & Zeiger, E. (2015). *Plant Physiology and Development* (6th ed.). Sinauer Associates.
- Tsega, Y.C., Devi-Prasad, A.G. (2014) Variation in air pollution tolerance index and anticipated performance index of roadside plants in Mysore, India, *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 35: 185-190